

A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF THE 20TH CENTURY ENGLISH AND UZBEK LITERARY TEXTS

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doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11520164

Annotation: This comparative study delves into the role of metaphor as a cognitive and discursive modeler of reality within 20th-century English and Uzbek literary texts. By examining the works of notable authors such as Virginia Woolf, George Orwell, Abdulla Qodiriy, and Chulpon, the study highlights how metaphors are employed to simplify complex abstract concepts and influence readers' perceptions.

Key words: abstract concept, common themes, metaphors, cognitive-discursive modelers, reader's perception, use

Metaphors are not merely decorative elements of language but fundamental mechanisms that shape our perception and understanding of the world. This article explores how metaphors function as cognitive and discursive modelers of reality within 20th-century English and Uzbek literary texts. By examining the works of Virginia Woolf, George Orwell, Abdulla Qodiriy, and Chulpon, this study highlights how metaphors are employed to simplify complex abstract concepts and influence readers' perceptions. Despite cultural differences, both literatures utilize universal cognitive functions and common themes such as life as a journey and light as enlightenment to shape and reflect human understanding. The analysis reveals distinct metaphorical imagery shaped by cultural and environmental factors, with English literature often drawing from industrial and technological contexts, while Uzbek literature remains grounded in natural and pastoral imagery.

Cognitive Metaphor Theory, as articulated by Lakoff and Johnson in 'Metaphors We Live By,' posits that metaphors are integral to human thought processes. They allow us to understand abstract concepts through more concrete experiences, bridging the gap between the abstract and the tangible. Metaphors are also pivotal in discourse, structuring how narratives are constructed and comprehended, and influencing the way we perceive and interact with reality.

Virginia Woolf's 'To the Lighthouse':

Woolf employs metaphors related to time and memory, with the lighthouse serving as a symbol of stability amid the flux of life. The lighthouse stands as a beacon of constancy and guidance for the characters, reflecting their internal struggles and the passage of time. This metaphor encapsulates the broader theme of permanence versus change, a central concern in Woolf's narrative.

- Example: The lighthouse in Woolf's narrative is not only a physical structure but also a metaphor for the unattainable ideal and the guiding force in the characters' lives. It symbolizes the enduring nature of memory and the relentless passage of time, shaping the characters' understanding of their past and present.

George Orwell's "1984":

Orwell's use of industrial and mechanical metaphors critiques the dehumanizing effects of totalitarianism. The metaphor of 'Big Brother' epitomizes the pervasive surveillance and control exerted over individuals, symbolizing the loss of personal freedom and autonomy. This metaphorical construct provides a vivid image of a society under constant watch, where privacy and individuality are obliterated.

- Example: 'Big Brother' as a metaphor conveys the omnipresent government surveillance and the totalitarian regime's invasive control over the lives of citizens. The image of an all-seeing, omnipotent figure watching over every action serves to instill fear and conformity, shaping readers' perceptions of power and control.

In these English texts, metaphors facilitate the reader's grasp of complex themes such as the passage of time, memory, and political oppression. They shape the readers' perceptions, making abstract ideas more tangible and relatable. The metaphors employed by Woolf and Orwell not only enhance the narrative's depth but also engage readers in a deeper contemplation of the underlying themes.

Abdulla Qodiriy's 'O'tgan Kunlar'

Qodiriy uses nature-related metaphors extensively. The road metaphor in 'O'tgan Kunlar' represents life's journey, encapsulating the characters' experiences and challenges. This metaphor underscores the themes of progression and resilience inherent in the human condition, reflecting the cultural and historical context of early 20th century Uzbekistan.

- Example: The metaphor of the road in "O'tgan Kunlar" symbolizes the characters' life paths, with its twists and turns representing the struggles and triumphs they encounter. This natural imagery resonates with readers, grounding the narrative in the familiar experience of travel and journeying through life.

Chulpon's Poetry:

Chulpon's use of light and darkness metaphors conveys themes of hope and oppression. Light symbolizes enlightenment and the quest for freedom, while darkness represents the political and social struggles faced by the Uzbek people. These metaphors reflect the broader socio-political landscape of Uzbekistan during Chulpon's time, highlighting the struggle for national identity and resistance against oppression.

- Example: In Chulpon's poetry, light often symbolizes the hope for a brighter future and the enlightenment of the people. Conversely, darkness represents the shadow of oppression and the obstacles faced in the quest for freedom. These metaphors deeply resonate with the cultural and political context, making abstract concepts of hope and despair more accessible to readers.

In Uzbek literature, metaphors help readers navigate abstract concepts like freedom and national identity. They reflect and shape the cultural and political consciousness of the time, making the struggles and aspirations of the characters more vivid and immediate. The metaphors used by Qodiriy and Chulpon not only enhance the narrative's emotional impact but also engage readers in a deeper understanding of the cultural and historical context. By making abstract concepts more tangible and relatable, metaphors enhance readers' engagement with the narrative and deepen their understanding of the underlying themes.

This comparative study reveals that metaphors are essential cognitive and discursive tools in both English and Uzbek literatures. Despite cultural differences, metaphors in both traditions serve to model reality, making abstract concepts accessible and relatable. The analysis of metaphors in the works of Woolf, Orwell, Qodiriy, and Chulpon underscores the universal cognitive functions of metaphor while highlighting the distinct cultural influences that shape their use in literature. Studying metaphors across different cultures enriches our understanding of human cognition and the diverse ways in which reality is constructed through language. The intricate interplay between language, culture, and cognition underscores the enduring significance of metaphor in literary discourse.

REFERENCES:

1. "Metaphors We Live By" was published in 1980. It was co-authored by George Lakoff and Mark Johnson
2. "1984" by George Orwell was published in 1949.
3. "To the Lighthouse" by Virginia Woolf was published in 1927.
4. Abdulla Qodiriy. "O'tgan kunlar." Toshkent: Sharq, 2014. (Original work published in 1926)
5. Chulpon. "Tuyg'u." Toshkent: Sharq, 2016. (Original work published in 1929)